

DIRECTIONS FOR HEALTH DEVELOPMENT IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The fight against physical culture and sports, diseases, harmful imprisonment in the external environment is an important tool for healthy education. The article in the article in the development of a healthy lifestyle, of which they cover educational issues.*

Keywords: *organism, environment, health, upbringing, lifestyle, activity, power.*

The student's healthy lifestyle depends on the directions, worldview, social and moral experience of his value. Values developed by the Company always do not meet the values of the student's healthy lifestyle. The student's identity has a real ability to choose the forms of life and the types of actions that are important to him, each student forms his action and thinking form. Man is able to influence the content of the group or community of a group or community.

The study conducted by pedagogical scientist D.J. Sharipova is aimed at studying the problems of organizing students' hygienic education. The research is aimed at the development of the content of the experience of the existing problems in this regard, the organization of the urgency of the problem, as well as the organization of hygienic organization in the form of an integrated system of development.

Students are important for the formation of a healthy lifestyle in young people in this process. To maintain the health of students, follow the following:

- strengthening schools, family and public cooperation;
- promoting work aimed at the formation of medical-hygienic culture between parents;
- organization of regular monitoring of medical examination and monitoring of their physical and mental development, etc., etc.

Healthy lifestyles, health liability is formed as part of the general cultural development, it is manifested in the unity of the stylistic features of behavior, in the unit of stylistic features of behavior, in accordance with the ability to comply with its ideas of life.

Health is not the lack of a sign of disease, but a complete physical, mental and social well-being.

There are three main components in the health structure:

Physical health is integral indicators of the body's main physiological systems are the state of the body that is changeable by the environment, which is within the limits of physiological norms.

Mental health is an intellectual, emotional and conscious impact of intellectual, emotional and consciousness with a social environment that is sufficient to a particular society.

Social health is the structure of information models of information models that ensure the level of spiritual and moral manifestation, and the level of food, living conditions, labor and recreation conditions.

A healthy lifestyle is a lifestyle aimed at maintaining human health, prevention of diseases, and strengthening the entire body of the human body.

The main components of a healthy lifestyle include:

- Labor and recreation order;
- Sleeping;
- diet;
- organization of physical activity;
- adherence to the requirements of sanitary, hygiene, hardening;
- Prevention of bad habits;
- Interpersonal communication culture;
- Psychophysiological regulation of the organism;
- Culture of sexual behavior.

The order of labor and recreation should be individually, i.e. the student's unique conditions, health status corresponds to the performance level, personal interests and inclinations.

It is important to know that the work and the holiday regime is directly related to adaptation processes. If a person's adaptation reserves end, it will begin to experience the inconvenience, fatigue and diseases.

Establishment of sleep is a form of daily rest. The sleeping amount of sleep 7.5-8 hours for the student should be considered as a usual norm. Sleeping hours cannot be considered as a stock of time, which can be used frequently and for other purposes. Permanent insomnia can lead to a decrease in work, fatigue and annoyance.

Rational nutrition is that it is consuming physiologically food, taking into account the sex, age, labor and other factors. Nutrition is based on the following principles: achieving energy balance; The main nutrients are proteins, oils, carbohydrates, vitamins, the correct ratio between minerals. The body needs to meet the need for water.

The organization of physical activity is one of the mandatory factors of a healthy lifestyle for students. A large number of people engaged in intellectual labor has limited physical activity. It also applies to students. Therefore, the most important task is to determine the optimal and maximum modes of physical activity.

The main causes that hinder students from a healthy lifestyle are as a rule, the lack of time and lack of will, because today many students will train reading with work. Currently, in the socio-cultural sphere, there are wide range of opportunities for the organization of their free time. However, instead of the activities that help most students help socially cultural development, they choose entertainment that stops and even destroys development.

The next component of the formation of a healthy lifestyle is to abandon all bad habits. These include drug use, alcohol and smoking. Bad customs break health significantly, reduce life expectancy and adversely affect the performance of future children and health. As a rule, people start to win a healthy lifestyle through bad habits, especially smoking. Alcohol is particularly adversely affect the body and physical condition of the student. Consumption of alcohol is always associated with social consequences that harm others and people close to people and the whole society.

Physical culture and sports are an important tool for raising the younger generation. One of the most important qualities of a healthy body to effectively prevent diseases is to develop together with other components of endurance and other components of a healthy lifestyle. If we observe how their lifestyle affects our lives, we can draw the only right conclusion that a healthy lifestyle is necessary for everyone. After all, he helps us in all areas of our activities. Following

such a lifestyle, there is no problem in the health of each student, which is full of strength and enthusiasm, which in turn leads to training success.

Conclusion

For what has been analyzed above it can be inferred that it is necessary to strengthen the body in accordance with environmental conditions for healthy lives. There are people in marriage that some people are sick instantly. Is the ability to resist the positive state of health and harmful impressions in the external environment. The factors are factors to increase body resistance to the external environment through methods of stiffening, use of convenient exercise, bathing in cold water, and sustainable registration. Based on the effects of the body, the body is a slow connection mechanism for water, sun and air.

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